

A Study of Disclosure of the Qualification of the Independent Directors in the Annual Report by the Companies in India

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Abstract : *The motive of this study was to inspect the impact of the factors and features of disclosure of the qualification of the independent directors by companies in India. With this study, the authors wanted to determine association between the disclosure of the Qualification of Independent Directors (QIDR) in board and the age, size, origin, sector and profit of the companies in India. A binary logistic regression was undertaken to assess whether disclosure of qualification of the independent directors was related to the age, size, company's origin, sector and profit. The study has reflected that there is a significant difference between the QIDR and Non-QIDR (NQIDR) companies. The likelihood that the companies will publish the information regarding the qualification of the independent directors in the annual report is greater in the case of private sector companies and companies that have higher profits.*

Keywords : Binary Logistic Regression, India, National Stock Exchange, Qualification of Independent Directors, Disclosures.

Introduction

It is rightly said by Beaver (1989) that the effective functioning of the capital markets essentially depends on the disclosure made by the companies. In fact, Lev (1992) rightly pointed out that it is vital to have precise and accurate information about the performance potential of the companies, so that the money allocated in the stock markets bears fruits. There are two ways by which the information disclosure can create value, first is by directly narrowing down the information gap and thus reducing the uncertainty of the investors about the company and second is by indirectly enhancing value-creating activities through

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a reduced cost of capital and better terms of trade between the suppliers and customers. In the recent years a lot of attention has been paid to the information disseminated by the companies through various means viz., annual reports, websites, news reports etc. With the increased level of information dissemination there is a need to focus on the investor protection, corporate governance, corporate disclosures, etc because the quality of information disclosed by the companies has a great impact on the investment decision made by the investor (Elliot et. Al. 1994).

Types of Disclosures

The word disclosure includes a wide spectrum of information disclosed by the company which is classified as mandatory and voluntary disclosure. When the company is bound by law to disclose certain information at specific times and format it is called mandatory disclosure. For instance, information disclosed regarding the financial performance of the company in its annual report involves adherence to various laws, along with that it has to be presented in the format prescribed under the law. Along with that companies have to stick to the time frame provided under the law. If a company fails to follow these norms there are provisions for strict punishment and fines. So, it is extremely important for the companies not to deviate from these requirements. Company must also ensure that the information presented in these financial statements is correct and is backed by evidences i.e., audited results are presented in the annual report. The stakeholders of the companies, the potential investors, regulatory authorities, etc are also interested in information beyond the ones which are mandatory to be disclosed by the company, this information is nothing but the voluntary disclosure made by the company. This information, by default is considered to be valuable for the various stakeholders of the company and is crucial in order to assess the correct position of the company. For instance, the information disclosed by the company in the annual report under the discretionary requirements section, media reports, earning calls, etc. Nowadays with the improved means of communication disclosure can be made by the company through several means. Investors feel the need to know more about the company and its future growth prospects given the uncertainty of returns. If credible information disseminated from the insiders of the company, it helps boost the investor confidence and reduces the information asymmetry. This automatically enhances the usefulness of the financial statements and other mandatory information disclosed by the company. It is seen that few companies restrict themselves to the mandatory disclosure and hesitate to make voluntary

disclosures while few choose to have a mixture of both in their disclosure pattern, this important aspect was highlighted by Verrechia (1983).

The Need for Corporate Disclosures

The disclosure of financial information by the company plays an integral part in decision making both at individual and corporate level (Elsayed et. Al. 2010). The financial reporting practices that evolved during the early twenty-first century defined the disclosure practices we find today. Its significance keeps on increasing as the financial reporting practices transform in this highly informed era. Today as the investors find it very difficult to make investment decisions given the complexities and situations, disclosure finds more and more relevance in the business world and it is equally important to study and make necessary improvements in this field. Regulatory authorities and the government of India has been constantly emphasizing on the need to make more and more quality disclosure so that it reduces the information asymmetry between the providers and users of disclosure information.

Laws Pertaining to Disclosure of the Board in Companies in India

Over the years several attempts have been made to encourage companies to make more disclosure in their financial statements, press release etc. SEBI (2005) amended the existing Listing Agreement Clause 49 and it said that all existing listed companies with a paid-up share capital of Rs. 3 crores or more or with a net worth of Rs.25 crores or more shall submit quarterly compliance report to the stock exchanges. The stock exchanges also have to ensure that all provisions of the clause 49 have been complied with by the company seeking listing for the first time. For this the company has to setup its board and constituted committees i.e., Audit Committee, Shareholders / Investors Grievances Committee etc., in accordance with revised clause before seeking in principle approval for listing. A separate cell with identified personnel is maintained by the stock exchanges to monitor the compliance with the provisions of the revised clause 49 on corporate governance. A consolidated report is prepared by the stock exchanges after receiving the compliance reports from the companies and is submitted to SEBI within 60 days from the end of each quarter.

SEBI (2008) amended the disclosure requirements of the board in Annexure 1D of clause 49 of listed companies. It said that

“a non-executive chairman is allowed to maintain an office for the chairman. These expenses are to be borne by the company and he shall receive the

reimbursement for any expense borne by him for performing his duties. The tenure of the Independent Directors on the Board of a company shall not exceed nine years. The independent directors who are qualified and have the required experience shall be appointed by the company. The company may check the requisite details before the appointment of the independent directors”.

Affairs (2009) issued Corporate Social Responsibility Voluntary Guidelines in order to assist and encourage companies to make more disclosures. The fundamental principles listed in the guidelines include formulation of a CSR policy along with participation of various levels of executives and approved by the board. The core elements of the guidelines emphasise on care for all stakeholders i.e., respecting the interests of and being responsive towards shareholders, develop a mechanism to engage with stakeholders, inform them of innate risks and lessen their impact. On the ethical functionality, the companies must engage into governance with ethics, transparency and accountability.

Companies Act (2013) defines the qualifications of an independent director in the following manner :

Section 149(6) defines an independent director of a company as, “a person who doesn’t hold the position of either a managing director or whole-time or nominee director. The board believes that the person has requisite experience and skills. The person or his relative is not or was not the promoter or related to the promoters or directors of the company (holding, subsidiary or associate company) during the current financial year or two immediately preceding financial years. In case of any transaction during the two immediately preceding financial years or during the current financial year, it should not exceed two per cent of the gross turnover/total income/fifty lakh rupees whichever is lower. The person or his relative is or has not held any important managerial post in the company (holding, subsidiary or associate) in three financial years immediately preceding the financial year (year of appointment). He is or was not an employee or owner or a partner in the company in the immediately preceding three financial years (year of appointment) in the following firms or institutions- an audit firm, company secretary, cost auditor, legal consultancy firm. The person or his relative does not hold voting power of the company (two per cent. or more). The person is not the Chief Executive or director of any Non-profit organisation (NGO) that is in receipt of twenty-five per cent. or more from the promoters/directors/company (holding, subsidiary or associate) that holds voting powers (two per cent. or more)”.

Section 149(7) emphasises that each and every independent director “shall give a declaration that he/she fulfils the criteria of independence or are qualified to be an independent director under sub-section (6) at his/her first board meeting and at every first board meeting of every financial year”.

Review of Literature

In order to adhere to the principles of the corporate governance the company needs to be more transparent regarding its day-to-day operations (Harun et Al. 2018). Bamber (2010) said that the high-profile strategic operational and financing decisions like mergers, acquisitions, strategic marketing, product expansion etc are taken by the top-level management who work as the economic agents. They are more inclined towards these key decisions however when it comes to making secondary decisions like making choices regarding disclosure, they do not seem to have much effect. While making a disclosure, utmost care needs to be taken as these decisions are enigmatic and obscure. These decisions require trade-off among several contradictory goals, i.e., they need to disclose information in a way that it benefits the investors, doesn't increase the litigation risk of the company and doesn't let the competitors know the insights of their business, these important revelations were made in a study by Dye (1986); (Evans et. Al. 2002). The disclosure level of the companies can be ascertained by the disclosure index which comprises of both voluntary as well as mandatory disclosures made by the company. This disclosure index can be calculated from the information revealed by the companies in their annual report, websites, and other media (Marston et. Al. 1991). The financial and non-financial information revealed by the company in its annual report and other media reports is known as disclosure (Gibbins et Al. 1990). Ackerlof (1970); Trueman (1986) found in their study that disclosure of information is beneficial to all the stakeholders of the firm. It is strongly dependent on the signalling managers capability to interpret and predict the changes in the economic environment of the business. The orientation of the investors' expectations with the managers' assessment is really important (Ajinkya et. Al. 1984) and (King et Al. 1990). Skinner (1994) and (Kasznik et. Al. 1995) observed that the management needs to prevent the negative news, as it is important to attract new capital (Frankel et al. 1995). Time and degree of accuracy of the information disclosed by the companies enhances its value in the eyes of the investors (Elliot et. Al. 1994). The more the information disclosed by the company the more it creates a positive effect on its stock market price (Lev et. Al. 1990). The disclosures made by the firm has various ramifications on both the management and the stakeholders of the firm as it reflects the firm's

position (Gibbins et Al. 1992). When a firm witnesses a change in the credit ratings it tends to make more voluntary disclosures regarding its future prospects and decisions, this was an important finding of the study conducted by He (2018). The companies with large ownership concentration namely the public limited companies tend to make more financial information disclosure through the electronic media (Tatjana et Al. 2018). Fernando (2017) found out in his study that the stock price movement is less during the announcement of the earnings and the companies make more disclosure to increase the trading volume. Cassar (2018) suggested that the performance and holdings of the high return hedge funds are not disclosed by the managers due to high proprietary cost. Lin (2018) said that the increase in the institutional ownership leads to enhancement in the information environment which creates pressure on the other rival firms in the industry to disclose more information. Hales (2018) discovered that the employee reviews about the companies on various social networking platforms are helpful in predicting the future corporate disclosures by the company. Golden (2017) argued that firms controlled by members of the same family offsets the stock-based incentives which is the motivation for managers to make timely disclosures.

Objectives of the Study

The study is mainly confined to achieve the following objectives:

1. To study and analyse the relationship between the financial/non-financial factors and the disclosure of the qualification of the independent directors of the board of the companies in India.
2. To identify areas where disclosure of the qualification of the independent directors made by the company can be improved and suggest measures if any.

Scope of the Study

The study focuses on the association between the financial aspects (namely size, profit), non-financial aspects (namely age, sector and origin of the company) and the disclosure made by the company regarding the qualification of the independent directors (QIDR) of the company (Tatjana et al. 2018). There has been a lot of study on the disclosure of information by the companies, banks and other institutions across the globe but very little focus has been given to disclosure of information in annual reports of the firms in India in particular. The study aims to study the disclosure level of the Indian companies that are listed on the NSE. There is a need to study the numerous issues surrounding the disclosure by the companies in India and their impact.

Sample for the Study

Sample selection for the study has been done through purposive sampling technique. The selected companies are listed on the NSE. The period of study is 2020-2021. Banks and other financial institutions are kept outside the purview of the study in order to avoid any variations in regulations. The study aims to perform an over the sector comparison of the disclosure of the board made by the companies. The sample for the study consists of 537 public and private sector companies operating in India.

Period of the Study

The study has been conducted for a period of 1 year i.e., 2020-2021.

Data Collection, Analysis and Interpretation

The study has been primarily based on secondary data. The various sources of data are the annual reports published by the firms, the official website of the firms, the official website of Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock Exchange (NSE), reports and SEBI guidelines, etc. Various statistical tools like Percentage, Comparative Analysis, Unweighted disclosure Index, Content Analysis, Test of Significance, binary logistic regression etc. has been applied to draw useful inferences out of the study. Statistical software like MS Excel, SPSS, etc. has been used for the analysis.

Hypotheses Development

The company's profitability and age are not significantly related to the voluntary internet financial reporting done by the company (Tatjana et Al. 2018). Older the company give more insights about their activities as compared to young companies because they are more immune to shocks (Owusu et. Al. 1998), Al-Shammari (2007). So, we decided to study the relationship between age and the QIDR and the following hypothesis was developed

H1 : There is a positive association between the age of a company and the disclosure of the qualification of independent directors in the annual report.

Disclosure made by the company depends on the size of the company because it requires a lot of resources to be able to deal with bulk information and presenting it in a way that it reaps benefits for the company (Singhvi et. Al. 1971), Buzby (1975), Cooke (1989), (Watson et Al. 2002), and (Abdullah et. Al. 2008). Thus, we tried to inspect this relationship in the light of QIDR.

H2 : There is a positive association between the size of a company and the disclosure of the qualification of independent directors in the annual report.

There is a positive impact of foreign ownership on corporate social responsibility disclosure (Khan et Al. 2013). There is a positive relationship between foreign institutional ownership and voluntary disclosure (Ling et Al. 2012). Huafang (2007) found that the higher the block holder ownership and foreign listing/shares ownership, the higher is the voluntary disclosure. Companies which have their origin in a developed country make more social and environmental disclosures than companies which have their origin in developing countries (Adams et Al. 1998), (Kolk et Al. 2001), (Hackston et. Al. 1996), Jahamani (2003), (Niskala et. Al. 1995), (Stanwick et. Al. 2006). Thus, we intend to study the relationship between the origin of the company i.e., Indian or foreign company and QIDR

H3 : There is a positive association between the origin of a company and the disclosure of the qualification of independent directors in the annual report.

Subramanian (2006) concluded that there were no differences in disclosure pattern of public/private sector companies, as far as financial transparency and information disclosure were concerned. Since very few efforts have been made to unearth the relationship between the sector of the company (public or private sector company) and QIDR, we developed the following hypothesis.

H4 : There is a positive association between the sector of a company and the disclosure of the qualification of independent directors in the annual report.

The companies which earn a lot of profits tend to disclose more to signal the investors that the company is profitable and several studies have examined this relationship but the results are different in different situations (Oyelere et Al. 2003). There is no correlation between company's profitability and internet financial reporting (Marston et al. 2004), Marston (2003), Al-Shammari (2007), (Damaso et. Al. 2011) and (Mohamed et Al. 2015). Pervan (2006), Al-Moghawli (2009), (Homayoun et al. 2010) said that there is a positive correlation between profitability and IFR. So, in connection with the prior studies we developed the following hypothesis :

H5 : There is a positive association between the profit of a company and the disclosure of the qualification of independent directors in the annual report.

Experimental Procedure

The data was obtained from the companies listed on the national stock exchange and using purposive sampling technique 537 companies were selected for the purpose of conducting binary logistic regression. Information regarding the disclosure of the board made by the companies in accordance with the Listing Agreement Clause 49 Annexure 1D, Companies Act 1956, Companies Act 2013, Listing Obligations and Disclosure Requirements Regulations 2015 was collected. Since, the disclosure pattern of the board by the companies did not show any significant changes except the qualification of the independent directors. The study focussed only on disclosure of the QIDR. The list of dependent and independent variables is shown in Table-1. The purpose of the study was to determine the factors which separate the QIDR companies from the NQIDR companies. For this study, the dependent variable was classified as a binary choice between a QIDR company and an NQIDR company.

The descriptive statistics of the independent variables for both groups of companies are shown in Table-2. For the variables that measure the company's age, size (market capitalization) and profit, the average values are higher in the NQIDR companies. The Table does not include the variables "Origin" and "Sector", as they belong to the group of descriptive variables. There were 487 Indian and 37 Non-Indian Companies making QIDR disclosure and there were 40 public sector and 484 private sector companies making QIDR disclosure. However, there were 12 Indian and 1 Non-Indian company in the NQIDR category and 6 public sector and 7 private sector companies in the NQIDR category.

To test hypothesis, we used binary logistic regression analysis, since our dependent variable and one independent variable is dichotomous as followed by Jaccard (2001). We used dummy variables of '0' for the 'non- disclosure' and '1' for the 'disclosure'. All independent variables and control variables were entered simultaneously. Following Field (2009), we first checked for multicollinearity using variance inflation factor analysis (VIF), and found no evidence of multicollinearity in the logistic regression model. A VIF value greater than 10, for any variable indicates multicollinearity. The VIF of the two continuous variables in the study was 1. We also inspected the standardized residuals and deviance statistics (Cook's distance). No standardized residuals exceeded 3, and no Cook's distance exceeded 1, which also indicated an acceptable model fit as suggested by Field (2009). The Omnibus test of model coefficients (model chi-square=20.71; df=5; p=0.001) the significant p value indicates that the full model

was a good fit, which also indicates an improvement over the baseline model. The Hosmer and Lemeshow Test (chi-square = 8.499; df = 8; p = .386) the insignificant p value indicated that the full model was a good fit.

Table-1 : The List of Variables

Variables	Indicator	Measuring
Dependent		
QIDR	Disclosure of Qualification of Independent Directors (in the company's annual report)	Dummy (1 = QIDR company, 0 = NQIDR)
Independent		
Age	Company's Age	Company's age in years
Size	Market capitalization	Market capitalization of the company
Origin	Country of Origin of the company	Dummy (1= Indian company, 0 = Non-Indian company)
Sector	Sector	Dummy (1= Private Sector company, 0 = Public Sector Company)
Profit	Profit of the company	Profit before extraordinary items and tax

Note : QIDR stands for qualification of independent directors companies and NQIDR stands for non-qualification of independent directors companies in Table-1 and Table-2.

Table-2 : Descriptive Statistics of the Independent Variables for both Company Groups

Independent Variable	Mean	S.E.	SD
Age			
QIDR	41.97	1.10	25.22
NQIDR	50.46	6.16	22.21
Size			
QIDR	2236390.35	321779.71	7365874.16
NQIDR	6350572.85	2469353.88	8903382.04
Profit			
QIDR	1191.95	141.61	3241.50
NQIDR	6619.79	2027.41	7309.91

Based on the logistic regression analysis results, it is evident that, out of the five variables included in the model, two may be considered statistically significant, namely, sector (Wald =8.734; p = 0.003), profit (Wald = 7.655; p= 0.006). All other variables, namely age, size, origin showed an insignificant effect on the QIDR. On the basis of the results from Table 3, a regression model equation can be formed

$$\text{Log} [(p / (1-p))] = 4.436 -1.870 \beta_1 + 0.000 \beta_2$$

The variables in the equation also give us Exp (B):

$$\text{Odds} [(p / (1-p))] = e^{84.435 + 0.154 \beta_1 + 1.000 \beta_2}$$

Where, β_1 = Sector and β_2 = Profit

H4 can also be confirmed because the “sector” variable had a significant correlation with the disclosure of qualification of the independent directors in the annual report. For every one-point increase in sector, the odds of QIDR disclosure increased by a factor of 0.154 (-84.60 per cent), with all other factors being equal. However, contrasting results were reported by Subramanian (2006).

Table-3 : Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp (B)
Full model						
Sector	-1.870	0.633	8.734	1	0.003	0.154
Profit	0.000	0.000	7.655	1	0.006	1.000
Constant	4.436	0.401	122.070	1	0.000	84.435

The “profit” variable measured the company’s profits. A statistically significant correlation was detected in the variable “profit”. As a result, the H5 can be confirmed partially with 95 per cent reliability because of the positive correlation between the company’s profit and QIDR disclosure in the annual report. For every one-point increase in the profit, the odds of the QIDR disclosure increased by a factor of 1.000 (0 per cent), with all other factors being equal. Similar results were obtained by (Oyelere et Al., 2003).

However, this study was unable to confirm three hypotheses, namely, hypotheses H1, H2 and H3, which refer to the impact of age, size, origin on the disclosure of QIDR in the annual report.

Conclusion

The paper presents the study on the factors according to which the companies which publish the disclosures of qualification of independent directors in their annual report (QIDR companies) differentiate from the companies that decided not to publish them (NQIDR companies). The study was carried out on a sample of companies in India (n = 537). It was discovered that most of them report QIDR. In the continuation of the study, a logistic regression analysis was used to formulate a model, with the help of which we identified the factors that affect the higher probability that the companies will publish the information regarding the qualification of independent directors in their annual report. To this end, a dependent variable was formulated, which was binary encoded (companies that report i.e., the QIDR and companies that do not report i.e., the NQIDR). The independent variables were related to the age, size, origin, sector, profit. The statistically significant variables, which affect the higher probability that the companies will report QIDR, are the following: company's sector (i.e., public sector or private sector), profit. The variables measuring the company's age, size, origin did not turn out to be significant statistically. The study was limited only to the determination of factors by which the QIDR companies differ from the NQIDR companies. However, the users' points of view in relation to the QIDR were not observed, which may present the subject of further studies. Such study would allow us to obtain the users' feedback in regard to the content and the method of presentation. The information could be used by the companies in formulating the strategy to present the information regarding the independent directors. It might also encourage the companies who do not use the QIDR to learn about the advantages and opportunities offered by it. Internet and other media can be used to shift from the traditional paper-based reporting to internet reporting in the future.

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